

**SIGNIFICANCE OF RELATIONS FOR TRANSLATION: -TAI ELEMENT IN NP₁+P_(-TAI)+NP₂
CONSTRUCTION OF MONGOLIAN INTO ENGLISH**

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Abstract

The syntactic and semantically relevant grammatical relations (henceforth, the grammatical relation/s) of any linguistic elements play a crucial role in a language. As their representative, this study examines the grammatical relations of -TAI element focusing on its syntactic properties.

The -TAI is the second most active grammatical element in the Mongolian language as it functions as a suffix that derives adjectives from nouns, and a comitative case marker. Among the various elements requiring more analysis, the relational element -TAI in NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction in Mongolian, which is tended to be translated into other languages literally, was selected for its complexity and ambiguity, specifically in translation, aiming to determine the significance of the syntactic and grammatical relations of the corresponding element from a linguistic point of view for translation into English as a non-cognate language of Mongolian.

Upon analysing the given linguistic facts, it becomes evident that the -TAI element syntactically generates the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction through daughter relation between NP₁ and NP₂ and denotes a general grammatical relation 'a trace or result of an action that has already been performed'.

In conclusion, it is important to note that when the nouns in the NP₁ and NP₂ are replaced by each other or one another, the resulting construction remains structurally or syntactically identical but the grammatical relations of the -TAI in the construction is entirely changed into many, due to the distribution, lexical meaning, lexical entry and correlation of the nouns in the NP₁ and NP₂ in Mongolian that is a representative of all human languages universally.

Keywords: NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction, -TAI (relational) element, (semantically relevant) grammatical relations, I/E-structure, sister/daughter relation

1. Introduction

Mongolian, a language of the Altaic family, possesses an SOV (agglutinative) structure characterized by numerous verb syntagms, rendering the NP₁+P+NP₂ construction rather uncommon. In the context of Mongolian, this construction is predominantly generated by a relational element -IIN/-NII, alongside others: -TAI⁴⁴, -SHIG, MET, ADIL, -NII TUKHAI, -NII GADNAKH, -NII ÖMNÖKH which we have categorized as OTHER⁴⁵ in our studies. The elements in the latter category are significantly fewer in number compared to the former. Through this study, we focus on the -TAI element as mostly contributing to generate this NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction rather than other elements in this categorization OTHER which are adjuncts in the verb phrases (VPs).

First, our literature analysis has revealed a significant gap in this subject that requires further investigation. Second, translating is the process of converting one sign from one language into another. Although it appears to occur in the E-structure, it is, in fact, a process that is naturally performed in the E-structure via the I-structure. Conversely, the translation is commonly done in a literal way relying on the I-structure of

any elements in the source language. One representative is the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction specifically generated by the -TAI element in Mongolian which is translated into English using morphological, lexicological and syntactic methods; however, the specific contexts for employing each method remain ambiguous. An example *nomtoi khün* in Mongolian can be translated into English in three distinct alternatives (1-3) at least.

(1) *A person who has collected numbers of books or sutras*

(2) *A scholarly person / A person who is well-educated*

(3) *A person who is erudite and proficient in the best way of life according to the natural laws*

This is a big question about such methods or techniques which inevitably attracts more interests from language learners, teachers and researchers.

The major response to this question pertains directly to the I-structure or initial-structure of the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction. Definitely, it is inappropriate to investigate the grammatical relations of the -TAI element which holds a distinctive role in the con-

⁴⁴ Orthographically, the -TAI element has two alternatives in old Mongolian script: -TAI and -TEI; but three: -TAI, -TEI and -TOI in Cyrillic.

⁴⁵ We use this capital form 'OTHER' as the term of the classification, but the lowercase form 'other' as a general word in our studies.

struction of Mongolian, exclusively through this element, due to the fact that this element connects NP₁ and NP₂ in either side to generate the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction. That means the distributions, lexical meanings, lexical entry of the nouns occurred in the distribution of the NP₁ and NP₂ along with their correlations strongly influence changing the grammatical relations of the -TAI element in this construction. Consequently, the grammatical relations of the -TAI element in the construction can be defined without any limitation.

As a result, this study primarily aims to validate the aforementioned concept from a linguistic point of view, rendering this study methodologically significant for future researchers and scholars examining any language elements like the -TAI in the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction based on its I-structure not E-structure in order to translate into English and other languages.

2. Literature review

The literature review concerning the -TAI element, as a case marker, should commence with the researches on the case studies in the Mongolian language. In history of Mongolian linguistics, the case studies were initially introduced through the first grammar of Mongolian briefly entitled “Ankhadugar Jürkhen Tolt” written in 1243 by Sakya Pandita Kunga Gyeltsen (1182-1251) which has unfortunately not survived to the present day; however, it has been recorded in the subsequent grammar “Mongol üsegiin yosiig saitar nomloson khelnii chimeg” by Agvaandandar Lharampa. Since that time, it has been a fundamental subject of the Mongolian language studies according to D.Tumurtoogoo (1981:403–445), which have touched upon their classifications by Sh.Luvsanvandan (1951, 1955, 1964a, 1964b, 1968a, 1968b, 1968c; 1978), D.Tumurtoogoo (1981); M.Bazarragchaa (1997, 2005, 2008); their semantics by J.Street (1963), G.Abamasu (1977), D.Badamdorj (2001:94–104); M.Bazarragchaa (2005:141–149), Ts.Otgonsuren (2022); their alternatives and historical development by D.Tumurtoogoo (1968:250–252), P.Byambasan (1983:302–305), Ch.Altanzagas (1997), M.Saruul-Erdene (2002:38–42), Ts.Otgonsuren (2012); their functions by Sh.Luvsanvandan (2010), D.Zayabaatar et al., (2016), Ts.Otgonsuren (2017); and in accordance with universal grammar by V.Dashdavaa (2012), M.Uuganbayar (2009:109–111; 2011:62–66) and Ts.Otgonsuren (2022).

Even though, some independent studies on the -TAI element are notably limited as the followings: Sh.Ozawa (2002:61–64) first proposed that the suffixes -TAI and its alternatives -TU and -TAN were gender-specific and numerical distinctions: the -TAI indicated feminine and the -TU masculine, but the -TAN plural form in the Middle Mongolian language. Khasbagana (1996:321–322) further examined the aforementioned concept and determined that the -TAI was a feminine alternative of the -TU which employed to derive adjectives from nouns, with resulting words serving as adjectives that denoted the relations. Also, Norjin (1981:53) clarified that the -TAI element was a suffix to derive adjectives from nouns, with an abstract meaning from the literal meaning of the corresponding noun, and elucidated how to distinguish this suffix from the

comitative case marker. Ch.Altanzagas (1997) defined the distinction between the meanings of the -TAI and -TU elements in the modern Mongolian language and then examined the case system as well as the alternatives, origin, multiple meanings, forms, distributions and syntactic features of the -TAI element as comitative case marker. Ts.Otgonsuren (2012) defined some specific syntactic functions of the -TAI element and its alternatives -TU and -TAN in “the Secret History of the Mongols” based on their distributions preceding nouns, verbs, postpositions and conjunctions, and concluded that 1. The original meaning of the -TAI element which denoted the relations has evolved into a comitative case marker in Modern Mongolian; 2. The -TU has retained a solely modifying function for nouns; 3. The -TAN has served as a suffix for deriving nouns from adjectives.

3. Method

As the NP₁+P+NP₂ construction generally represents a higher-level of word and a lower-level of clause in grammatical hierarchy, its examination at the higher level - clause is methodologically crucial for a comprehensive definition of this construction.

In order to define the syntactic and grammatical relations of the -TAI element in the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction in Mongolian, the diachronic and synchronic approaches were followed:

a. Diachronic Analysis: We collected and analysed all occurrences using -TAI element and its alternatives in “the Secret History of the Mongols” which is considered to be a written monument of Mongolian language, literature, history, culture and tradition, etc. dated back to the 13th century for their structures and distributions.

b. Synchronic Analysis: We created a corpus of literature in Mongolian from which a large number of occurrences were collected and observed for some hypothesis, explanations, analysis, descriptions and then confirmations for some phenomena of the target element. As the core theory of this study, the following theories, principles, rules, etc. of the Universal Grammar, developed by N.Chomsky (1957, 1965, 1981, 1985) and followed by most linguists including P.Sells (1987), V.Cook (2000), A.Carnie (2000), are practically used like:

- The Phrase Structure Rule for the basic structure of the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction;
- Government, the Head Parameter and the X-bar theory for defining the syntactic and grammatical relations of the (relational) elements -TAI in the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction;
- The Transformation rule for the movements of the elements;
- The θ -theory for the definition of the grammatical relations of the elements and construction;
- Projection Principle for the requirement of the relevant and other elements in the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction, etc.

c. Mini-Survey Analysis: A descriptive quantitative mini-survey was conducted among 65 undergraduate English majors at the National University of Mon-

golia to explore how learners navigate the relation between the English preposition WITH and the Mongolian suffix -TAI.

4. Results

To conduct this study comprehensively, a three-fold analytical approach was employed. The first phase involves a diachronic analysis, comparing the -TAI element and its alternatives within 13th-century texts to establish a historical baseline. This is followed by a synchronic analysis to examine its modern manifestations, and finally, a learner survey to investigate the practical application of these relations in translation.

4.1. Diachronic Analysis

Figure 1. Distributions of the -TAI element in “the Secret History of the Mongols”

(4) a....*barqujin-qo'a-ca töre[k]sen alan-qo'a neretei ökin tere* (Rachewiltz, I, 1972:14, Section 8)

b. *That [was] the maiden which was born of Barqujin Go'a of ... and named Alan Go'a* (Cleaves,F.W, 1982:2)

c. ... *Barqujin-qo, ..., had given birth to the girl Alan Qo-a* (Urgunge Onon, 2001:40)

(5) a. ... *qunar mawu cilger bi qutuqtai sutai üjin-i quriyaju iregü bolun qotola merkit-e huntawu* (Rachewiltz, I, 1972:46, Section 111)

b. *I, qunar and bad Čilger, In gathering the happy and fortunate Üjin, Am become a plague unto all the Merkid* (Cleaves,F.W, 1982:46)

c. ... *Barqujin I, Cilger, who am doubly bad, became the keeper of the fortunate and mighty Lady, ...* (Urgunge Onon, 2001:92)

(6) a. ... *tende hö'elün-üjin ke'elitei būrūn...* (Rachewiltz, I, 1972:24, Section 59)

b. ... *then, when Hö'elün Üjin was with child, ... Činggis Qahan was born* (Cleaves,F.W, 1982:14)

c. *On his return, Lady Hö'elün was pregnant* (Urgunge Onon, 2001:56)

(7) a. ...*caqa'an teme'en kōljū qara'utai tergetei sōni-de dūlin yorciju...* (Rachewiltz, I, 1972:140, Section 244)

b....*it having been [yet] night, straightway harnessing a white camel, departed in a black cart, travelling all the night* (Cleaves,F.W, 1982:177)

c. ... *Mother harnessed her white camel to the black wooden-framed covered cart [that]*

A diachronic analysis was, as being peripheral to this study, conducted using the Secret History of the Mongols, a well-known historical and literary text from the Middle Mongolian period. A total of 59 occurrences of the -TAI element were identified (See also Figure 1): 41 occurred before noun phrase in NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction like in (4-5), 16 before verb phrase in NP+P_(-tai)+VP construction (6-7) and 2 before postposition (8). Notably, these distributions have remained stable over time. Out of the 41 occurrences, 33 functioned as relational elements like in (4), while 8 as suffixes like in (5) according to Ts.Otgonsuren (2012).

very night and travelled after them through the night ... (Urgunge Onon, 2001:226)

(8) a. ... *üdür mór-dür-iyen yabuju naratai-a kebte'ül-e javilaju qadana qonotuqai* (Rachewiltz, I, 1972:167, Section 278)

b. ... *after that the sun shall be set, let the nightguards seize and [thus] pass the night...* (Cleaves,F.W, 1982:220)

c. ... *are to follow their own paths [during] the day and, at sun [set], yield to the nightguards and spend the night outside* (Urgunge Onon, 2001:271)

In Middle Mongolian, the marker -a in the *nartai-a* in (8) functioned systematically as *aqui* serving as a functional equivalent to the English copular verb “to be”. Over time, this form underwent a process of reduction into the postposition -a. This transformation in its E-structure can be attributed to the principle of the language economy where phonetic and structural erosion occurs to optimise processing efficiency.

The considerably frequent occurrence of the -TAI element in the classical original (Mongoliin Nuuts Tovchoo, 2009) suggests that the -TAI element has gained prevalence in modern Mongolian, reflecting its development. In traditional linguistics, the initial noun preceding the -TAI element is considered to be a modifier of the noun that follows the -TAI element. But, the universal grammar implies that it functions as a suffix for deriving adjectives from nouns (NP₁+P_(suffix)+NP₂ construction), as well as a connector between the two nouns (NP₁ and NP₂) and relational element connecting them (NP₁+P_(relational element)+NP₂) construction, in the Middle and Modern Mongolian languages.

4.2. Synchronic Analysis

To further corroborate the findings from the diachronic analysis and examine specific features in the contemporary context, a synchronic analysis focused on the -TAI element in the $NP_1+P_{(-tai)}+NP_2$ construction which is the most ambiguous in the Modern Mongolian. We assembled a corpus of 84,000 words, in which 227 occurrences of the -TAI element in the $NP_1+P_{(-tai)}+NP_2$ construction were identified and analysed to develop hypotheses and confirmations. The quantity of these occurrences is notably substantial. The -TAI element predominantly serves to connect nouns to verbs

(N+V) as an adjunct, conveying the meanings with, together with or along with as a comitative case marker. It denotes such grammatical relations rather than connecting nouns to nouns (NP_1+NP_2) directly in a sister-relation; instead, it connects indirectly in a daughter-relation through the verb, which presents challenges for syntactic transformations in the E-structure.

Within the scope of our analysis of the 227 occurrences, the -TAI element in the $NP_1+P_{(-tai)}+NP_2$ construction in Modern Mongolian was classified into two fundamental types based on their syntactic properties as outlined below (See also the Figure 2).

Figure 2. Syntactic properties of the -TAI element in the $NP_1+P_{(-tai)}+NP_2$ construction in Modern Mongolian

a. Derivational suffix: 16 occurrences derived adjectives from nouns often expressing the meaning of possession. For example, *gaikhaltai khot* (a wonderful city) incorporates a noun *gaikhal* (a wonder) and the suffix -TAI, creating an adjective *gaikhaltai* (wonderful). This mirrors the English practice of adding the suffix -full to the noun wonder to derive the adjective wonderful.

b. Relational element: 211 occurrences showed that the -TAI element contributed the grammatical relation of with or together and possession. For example, the term *ünertei* (with scent) in the $NP_1+P_{(-tai)}+NP_2$ construction *ünertei us* (perfume) does not simply mean water with scent, but rather refers to a specific product, known as perfume.

The diachronic and synchronic analyses of the -TAI element in the Middle and Modern Mongolian languages generally reveals a stable ratio of the relational element to the derivational suffix both conveying the same meanings of possession and having. However, it is essential to underline that the fundamental aspect of these analyses pertains to the relational element -TAI in the $NP_1+P_{(-tai)}+NP_2$ construction in Modern Mongolian, distinguishing it from the derivational suffix -TAI.

4.3. Learner Mini-Survey Analysis

The third phase of the study specifically investigates how learners perceive and process the grammatical relations of the -TAI element within the Mongolian language. While the survey included a parallel English section for baseline comparison, this analysis focuses exclusively on the Mongolian data to determine whether Mongolian native speakers can correctly identify the syntactic head (the modified word) of the -TAI

element in their L1. The participants analyzed the Mongolian sentences categorized into two basic syntactic constructions: a. $NP+P_{(-tai)}+VP$ and b. $NP_1+P_{(-tai)}+NP_2$.

The analysis of 65 responses revealed a distinct pattern in how native speakers process the -TAI element:

a. $NP+P_{(-tai)}+VP$: Learners demonstrated high proficiency in recognizing -TAI as a verb modifier (Adjunct). In verb phrases extracted from the corpus, the majority correctly identified the relation to the predicate like in (9).

(9) a. *baiguullagatai ajillaj irjee*

b. *organization-SING, DET, COM work-PRSPRF*

c. *has worked with the organization*

This suggests that because Mongolian is a verb-prominent (SOV) language, speakers naturally gravitate toward connecting relational elements to the main verb.

b. $NP_1+P_{(-tai)}+NP_2$: It has two distinct constructions in Mongolian, which align with the functional distinctions established in Section 4.2. The first involves the derivational suffix, where learners processed a phrase such as (10):

(10) a. *gunigtai setgel*

b. *sadness-COM heart/feeling*

c. *sad feeling / sad heart*

In such NP constructions, the noun *gunig* (sadness) combines with the suffix -TAI to derive the adjective *gunigtai* (sad), directly modifying the head noun *setgel* (heart/feeling). Because this derivational process mirrors English adjective formation, accuracy was moderate. Learners often avoided mechanical or literal translations (e.g., *a heart with sadness*) and instead relied on semantic cues of "possession" rather than purely

syntactic analysis to correctly produce the adjective phrase.

Conversely, when processing the relational element (as distinguished in Section 4.2), the most significant finding was the remarkably low accuracy rate of 15.4% in translating these constructions. In complex phrases extracted from the corpus, learners frequently defaulted to a mechanical "Form-to-Form" translation. For instance, in the following phrase, they inserted the preposition WITH because of the -TAI suffix acting as an adjective derived from a noun like in (11):

- (11) a. *khorin dörvön salaa evertei ukhaa dönön buga*
 b. *twenty four branch antler-COM light bay four year old deer-SING, NOM*
 c. *a light bay four-year-old deer with twenty-four-tined antlers* (in literal translation based on its E-structure)

d. *a light bay four-year-old deer which has twenty-four-tined antlers* (in accurate translation based on its I-structure)

Common errors included treating it as a simple possession or instrumental adjunct, failing to recognize the deeper grammatical relation. A natural English translation would require a structural shift based on its I-structure. The learners' failure to recognize the exact relation between NP₁ and NP₂ led to these literal translation breakdowns.

The data confirms a critical blind spot in the processing of the I-structure in Mongolian. Native speakers tend to over-generalize the -TAI element as a verbal adjunct due to the SOV structure of the language. This failure to recognize -TAI as a noun-modifier in NP constructions causes "Form-to-Form" translation errors, where learners mechanically translate -TAI as with, missing the opportunity to use relative clauses or specific adjectives required in English.

Figure 3. Representation of the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction in the E-structure

As illustrated in the X-bar tree diagram above, the Mongolian relational element -TAI functions as the syntactic head (P), taking the preceding noun phrase *khorin dörvön salaa ever* (NP₁) as its complement to form a Postpositional Phrase (PP). Consequently, this entire PP acts as a modifier for the subsequent noun phrase *ukhaa dönön buga* (NP₂), merging under a single maximal projection, the highest NP node.

However, translating this E-structure literally into English using the preposition with (e.g., *a light bay four-year-old deer with twenty-four-tined antlers*) distorts the relation of possession, potentially implying an instrumental or comitative case (*as if the deer is merely standing next to or carrying the antlers*). Therefore, relying on its I-structure - which reveals the deeper grammatical relation of inalienable possession (i.e., *the deer inherently possesses the antlers growing on its head*) - proves that a structural shift using a relative clause (*a light bay four-year-old deer which has twenty-four-tined antlers*) is the most accurate and linguistically sound approach for translation.

5. Discussion

A word is not an element which occurs in any firmly fixed distribution in a sentence and solely conveys a certain meaning wherever it occurs. So it is general and abstract as a single element but it gets more

obvious and disambiguous in its relation to other elements within its higher level of the grammatical hierarchy - a phrase, clause and sentence then. Likewise, the -TAI element cannot be entirely defined in a lexicon or dictionary when it is a single element. The definitions of the grammatical relations of the -TAI element vary depending on which elements are connected by in the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction in particular. Although the fundamental relation of this element is possession, the relations are mutable based on the distribution, lexical meaning, lexical entry, and correlation of the nouns or noun phrases which occur in the distribution of the NP₁ and NP₂. As a result, the grammatical relations of the -TAI element in the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction is limitless like in (12-16), however their classification or systemisation is constrained, on contrary.

(12) a. *avdraaraa düüren nom sudartai övgön* (Rinchen B, 1945)

b. *book and sutra-PLU, COM (ACC) old man-SING, NOM*

c. *an old man with many books and sutras*

d. *an old man who has many books and sutras*

e. *an old man (who has) kept/collected many books and sutras* (in this context)

(13) a. *altan kharganatai tolgoi* (Lkhagvasuren B., 1979)

b. *caragana-COM (POSS) hill-SING, NOM*

c. *a hill with a full of caragana*
 d. *a hill (which is) covered in/dominated by caragana*

e. *a caragana-covered hill*

(14) a. *tsasan deer buugaad baisan nisdeg teregtei erliin bagiinkhan* (Ayurzana G., 2002)

b. *helicopter-SING, COM (TRANS) search and rescue team-SING, NOM*

c. *a search and rescue team with a helicopter*

d. *a search and rescue team who has a helicopter*

e. *a search and rescue team (who is) using a helicopter (in this context)*

(15) a. *ailiin aduund baisan daagatai güü-g avchrakh...* (Lkhagva Zh., 1970)

b. *foal-SING, COM (POSS) mare-SING, NOM*

c. *a mare with a foal*

d. *a mare (who) has a foal (in this context)*

e. *a mare (who is) followed by her foal (can be in other context in Mongolian)*

(16) a. *moritoi khün tsastai tald süreg chonoos zugtaad ...* (Jiang Rong, 2010)

b. *horse-SING, COM (ACT) man-SING, NOM*

c. *a man with a horse*

d. *a man (who is) riding a horse (in this context)*

e. *a man (who) has a horse (can be in other context in Mongolian)*

f. *a man (who) is lucky (can be in other context in Mongolian)*

But, all the relations of the -TAI element in the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction can be defined and elucidated entirely, abstracting this construction in its I-structure or initial-structure. The -TAI element is identified as a comitative case marker, serving as an adjunct that conveys meanings of ‘with’ and ‘together’ in verb phrase, and as the second active element after the -IIN/-NII element⁴⁶ in the NP₁+P+NP₂ construction in Mongolian. This property is expected to enhance the uniqueness of the -TAI element, which can be apparently evidenced in the following examples. Namely, the initial (17) reveals the grammatical relation in an abstract way that when the -TAI element connects *khas tamga* (a swastika sign) and *döröö* (stirrup) just in this specific linear order, it generally provides a distinct meaning *the stirrups with swastika sign* in its E-structure, but *the stirrups with a swastika sign engraved on* or *the stirrups on which a swastika sign has been engraved* in its I-structure or initial-structure regarding the lexical meanings, lexical entries and correlations of the both nouns in the NP₁ and NP₂.

(17) a. *Övög deedes chine khas tamgatai döröö-göö multalj...* (Galsansukh S., 1996)

b. *swastika sign-SING, COM (POSS) stirrup-e (PLU), NOM*

c. *stirrups with a swastika sign*

d. *stirrups which has a swastika sign*

e. *a pair of stirrup on each of which a swastika sign has been engraved.*

In the next example (18), the -TAI element connects the nouns *gerel* (light) and *tsonkh* (window) in the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction. If translated literally into English in its E-structure, it refers to the windows with lights indicating the windows that have lights or windows through which lights entered the rooms of the apartment (from outside into inside). As this context tells the windows of the rooms in which the lights have been turned on in its I-structure, it is plausibly confirmed that the grammatical relations of the -TAI element is quite variable in each context.

(18) a. *Zergeldee suutsnii barilguudad gereltei tsonkh olon, khöshigtei khöshigui, delgeestei delgeesgüi yanz бүр ...* (Bayarsaikhan P, 2017)

b. *light-e (PLU), COM (ACC) window-e (PLU), NOM*

c. *windows with lights*

d. *windows with the lights in the rooms*

e. *windows of the rooms in which the lights have been turned on*

In summary, the grammatical relations of the -TAI element depend upon the nouns which occur in the distributions of the NP₁ and NP₂; however, as the NP₂ serves as the head word in the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction in Mongolian which adhere to an SOV structure and the Head and Parameter Principle, the lexical meanings at first, and lexical entry and their correlation, as well as the syntactic relations: sister-relation and daughter-relation are also crucial in defining the grammatical relations of the -TAI element. For example, in the *tom tsartai makh* in the next example (19), the NP₂ governs the NP₁ with a meaning that the *makh* (flesh as NP₂) does not contain *tsar* (a big metal dish, as NP₁), but tells the result of an action which *some flesh was put/served on the big metal dish*. This kind of relation is capable to be represented through merely a daughter-relation, not a sister-relation according to the Universal Grammar.

(19) a. *Galsmaa gerees tom tsartai makh barin garch ireed bars bolon busad nokhdiig shagnalaa* (Jiang Rong, 2010)

⁴⁶ The author has defined through the I-structure that the -IIN/-NII elements in Mongolian indicate 22 grammatical relations, and OF in English around 22 at least (Otgonsuren Ts, 2022).

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c. *big metal dish*-SING, COM *flesh*-U, NOM

d. *some flesh with a big metal dish* (in literal translation based on its E-structure)

e. *some flesh on a big metal dish* (in semantic translation)

f. *some flesh which was put/served on a big metal dish* (in accurate translation based on its

I-structure)

The three examples (17-19) aim to highlight the capacity of the -TAI element that it denotes distinct grammatical relations connecting different nouns in the NP₁ and NP₂, despite generating the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction with the same distribution and function.

But it is intriguing that the grammatical relations of the -TAI element can be altered due to the distributions of the nouns changed in the NP₁ and NP₂, even

though the NP₁+P_(-tai)+NP₂ construction is generated by the same nouns as illustrated in the following example (20). Unfortunately, it is frequently ignored by English language learners specifically. All elements in the distribution of the NP₁ and NP₂ in the above mentioned example (19) keep their identical syntactic relations but exhibit a significant variation in grammatical relations radically when their distributions are reversed.

a. *makhtai tsar*

b.

c. *flesh-U, COM big metal dish-SING, NOM*

d. a big metal dish with some flesh (in literal translation based on its E-structure)

e. a big metal dish on which some flesh has been served (in accurate translation based on its I-structure)

6. Conclusion

Previously, the -TAI element in the $NP_1+P_{(-tai)}+NP_2$ construction was considered to consistently denote the grammatical relation of 'possession'. This study, however, has shown that the -TAI element functions syntactically by generating the $NP_1+P_{(-tai)}+NP_2$ construction through daughter relation between NP_1 and NP_2 and denotes a general grammatical relation of 'a trace or result of an action that has already been performed'. Despite this, the relevant element can, in an abstract way, denote nearly infinite grammatical relations in the I-structure, relying on the distributions, lexical meanings, lexical entries and correlations of all elements in the $NP_1+P_{(-tai)}+NP_2$ construction. This is because any individuals do not employ a single element when using a language, and the single elements lack the capacity to entirely express their ideas.

In summary, the phenomena observed on the relational element -TAI in the $NP_1+P_{(-tai)}+NP_2$ construction in this study reflects limitlessly to Mongolian, or English, as a fundamental property of human language. The human language acts as an external representation of human thought, that is to say, the human thought is encoded in the I-language, which is universal and embodied in the human mind, but articulated through the E-language. Hence, we should priorly define the I-structure that provides a more perfect alternative of translation in meaning and style.

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Abbreviations

ACC	Accusative
ACT	Action
COM	Comitative case
INSTR	Instrument
NOM	Nominative case
PLU	Plural
POSS	Possession
PRSPRF	Present Perfect Tense
SING	Singular
TRANS	Transportation
U	Uncountable